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Life as God's Most Sublime Gift

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The devastating spread of the Covid-19 pandemic has made most humans aware of the precariousness of life, a reality we have frequently taken for granted. Suddenly we feel overcome by a nagging feeling of helplessness. Everywhere we turn we only hear of the news of the menacingly advancing disease and the harrowing trail of suffering and death it has left behind. The brutal surge of the infection seems to spare no part of the world. In fact, the most affluent countries of the world, presumed to have been equipped with the most advanced health-care facilities, appear to be the most afflicted ones.

The ubiquitous reality of the lockdown has literally brought the world to its knees. Men and women who lived their lives with such intensity—many of whom often wished if only they could extend their days by a couple of hours more—now find their clocks moving at snail's pace! On the flipside it has given people time and opportunity to dwell on fundamental issues which our busy life had until now prevented us from paying any attention to. Social media platforms are awash with reflections that enlighten us on the enduring values that must undergird a healthy human life. While most people are convinced that our world will never be the same again post-Corona, some even think that Nature is getting back on us for the appalling harm we have been relentlessly inflicting on it.

120

The Sublime Gift of Life

One thing that dominates a large number of ruminations is the focus on the gift aspect of life. While the Corona virus has managed to set the world on edge, humanity has become aware that our tall claims about technological advancement and breakthrough scientific discoveries sound so hollow when confronted with a challenge like the raging force of the fast-spreading pandemic. There is no vaccine to protect ourselves from it and there is no effective cure if we become infected by it. While faith-seekers contend that their lives are in the hands of God, those who think that belief in any transcendent power is a luxury they can ill afford simply throw up their hands and stare at a sky that is full of only satellites and comets! But people on both sides of the divide are now deeply convinced that the gift of life cannot at all be taken for granted.

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The Nirbhaya Case

Even as the whole human effort is currently focused on holding on to dear life, my thoughts go back to how our system worked overtime to snuff out precious life from the four young convicts of the infamous Nirbhaya case just a few weeks ago, on March 20 this year. It is surely politically incorrect to say anything in defence of those nefarious predators or their chillingly ghastly crime. True they were put through the due process and their criminal intent was proved through a prolonged legal battle. My disagreement is with the nature of the punishment given to them. A lot of people felt acutely outraged when those men through their lawyers went about

121

resorting to one remedy after another to spare themselves from the finality of the death sentence. From review appeals to mercy petitions, the entire gamut of legal measures was run and perhaps exhausted before they were finally sent to the gallows. It was easy for us to condemn their delaying tactics, but we fail to remember they were fighting for their dear life.

People who spoke out against giving the capital punishment had understandably few sympathizers, even fewer supporters. Former Supreme Court judge, Justice Kurian Joseph, who publicly requested the authorities to transmute their punishment to life imprisonment, was ridiculed as a naïve follower of Jesus, who at one time studied for the priesthood. Senior advocate of the Supreme Court, Indira Jaisingh, was subjected to endless trolling for appealing to the victim's mother to forgive the murderers. At the end, the sticklers for the *lex talionis* (law of retaliation) of Hammurabi had their way and the four deeply anguished young men were done away with.

The mother of the unfortunate victim of the inhuman crime apparently expressed happiness at the case being brought to its desired conclusion and claimed that finally her daughter had got justice. One can understand a bitterly grieving mother's feelings, but the question of the quality of justice that she sought remains a moot point. Many of us think that retributive justice is more effective as a deterrent and more in keeping with the

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122

principles of law enforcement. But I think it is based on a rather primitive and unenlightened understanding of establishing true justice. For the emergence of a genuinely affirmative social system we must

rather have recourse to restorative justice. When a society chooses the path of restorative justice over against that of retributive justice, the healing touch that it imparts to the social system will be immensely more enduring. Its benefits will be for the long haul and will eventually be beneficial to even those siding with the victims.

Conclusion: God as the Sole Author of Life

Life is the most sublime of the gifts that we possess. God is the author of life and it is God's gratuitous gift to us. As the scenes currently unfolding before us prove it indisputably, we humans cannot gift life to anyone, cannot even safeguard it beyond a point. In a fit of anger an individual can snuff out another's life or a judicial system, after combing through labyrinthine evidences and by referring to flawless provisions of legal jurisprudence, can award the capital punishment to a convict. But all our individual and corporate resources put together cannot bring a dead man or woman back to life! It is indeed a sobering thought that humanity's resolute battle to contain the spread of the Corona virus should bring home to us.